

UDC 373.2:316.454.5

DOI: 10.15587/2519-4984.2022.257343

ORGANIZATION OF DIALOGUE INTERACTION OF ADULTS AND CHILDREN IN THE DEVELOPMENTAL ENVIRONMENT OF EARLY GROUPS

Natalia Gavrish, Olga Bessonova

The article considers the problem of organizing dialogic interaction of adults and children in the developmental environment of early age groups. The article presents the results of theoretical research on the concepts of "dialogue", "interaction", "dialogue interaction". It is determined, that in most scientific sources dialogue is considered as a form, method and means of social contacts, which is realized by the individual in the subject-subject interaction. Educational influences, focused on dialogic interaction, able to stimulate speech and interpersonal interaction between children, are just beginning to develop and do not have wide practical application. Based on the following ideas about dialogue, the development of dialogical interaction of adults and young children in the educational space of ZDO, it is necessary to focus on solving the following tasks: establishing emotional contact between participants in educational interaction; mastering verbal and nonverbal means of communication; ability to perform actions together with other participants in the educational process. The main models of dialogic interaction, their uniqueness and effectiveness are described, namely: interaction that encourages the child to active cognition (cognitive development occurs during interaction with objects, mastering texts, actions in a specially created space, and the core of such a system is active action), reorientation of the child's behavior in interaction with an adult (involves natural and logical changes in unwanted behavior of the child, which strengthens the child's sense of self-worth and shapes his/her character; the following types: sandwich, steps, triplets, pattern), supportive interaction task: to help the child to form a positive image of themselves, to realize their value and uniqueness; the following types: emotional, resource, co-existence support). The importance of maintaining consistency in the organization of interaction is emphasized: from the usual way in the usual conditions to the new way in the new unusual space. The algorithm of the organization of dialogue interaction is defined: I look, what the child does now; I feel and analyze what he/she needs now, what he/she expects from me; I give him/her what he/she needs. Emphasis is placed on the importance of compliance with speech strains when interacting with children early, compliance with the rules of communication by all participants in the educational process. Possibilities of application of the offered models of dialogue interaction in modern conditions of reforming of education in Ukraine are defined

Keywords: *dialogue, interaction, dialogue interaction, modelling of dialogue interaction, algorithm of construction of dialogue interaction*

How to cite:

Gavrish, N., Bessonova, O. (2022). Organization of dialogue interaction of adults and children in the developmental environment of early groups. ScienceRise: Pedagogical Education, 3 (48), 23–27. doi: <http://doi.org/10.15587/2519-4984.2022.257343>

© The Author(s) 2022

This is an open access article under the Creative Commons CC BY license hydrate

1. Introduction

The problem of dialogical interaction between teachers and young children in public education is becoming increasingly important. All activities in the real world, from human functioning to his/her sense of reality, are based on various types of interaction that he/she uses as a means of knowledge or tools. This is determined primarily by the essence of human - people live and act only in real connections and relationships with each other. Therefore, at the present stage of development of preschool education there is a need for active introduction of dialogical forms and methods of interaction between adult and young child, provided the child's subjective position in the activity and equal participation in heuristic dialogue with adults.

2. Literary review

The problem of dialogicity has been studied by scientists from antiquity to the present day. According to philosophers (Kant, Plato, Socrates), dialogue is the basis of existence, and human existence is always "coexistence" with other people [1]. The original concept of subject and object was developed by L. Feuerbach: an individual person does not carry a human essence, the human essence is transparent only in community and unity with other people, based only on the reality of differences between Me and You. His thoughts were developed in the works of the following thinkers (M. Bakhtin, V. Bibler, M. Buber, K. Jaspers, S. Arthur, S. Frank): dialogue is the most important condition for the existence and self-realization of the subject, which is carried out in many contacts with other subjects in the presence of

complications and differences between "Me and You". "The very existence of human (both external and internal) is the deepest communication... To be – means to be for another and through him/her – for yourself. Human has no sovereign territory, he/she is all and always on the border, looking inside him/herself, he/she looks into the eyes of another or the eyes of another"[2]. In the context of our research, the position of M. Buber and the system of relationships "Me and You", developed by him, deserve attention. For Martin Buber, dialogue is a special kind of being that unites us outside us, it is a constant movement towards the Other.

Research on the organization of dialogue is continued also by modern scientists. In their opinion, the process of communicative activity is a complex result of human interaction, which is open to each of its participants from a certain perspective, the source of which is the Self, and the limit – the Other [3]; signals the subject to make changes, gives him/her feedback, sets the limits of his/her impact on the environment [4]; the main thing in the dialogue is "not the truth of the discovery of new knowledge, but the truth of the process of existence of the dialogue" [5]; the active organizing attitude is manifested not only to the subject of joint activities, but also to the communication partner [6].

The analysis of the scientific literature shows that with a fairly broad appeal to the study of the concept of dialogic interaction, the scientific positions of the authors do not reveal the mechanisms of dialogic interaction of adults and young children in the developmental environment of early age groups.

3. Research aim and tasks

The aim of the research is to substantiate the mechanism of organization of dialogical interaction of adults and children in the developmental environment of early age groups by means of theoretical analysis of scientific sources.

To achieve this goal, the following tasks were set:

1. Based on the analysis of scientific sources to clarify the essence of the concepts of "dialogue", "interaction", "dialogue interaction".
2. To characterize the main models of dialogical interaction of adults and children in the developmental environment of early age groups, to prove their uniqueness and effectiveness.
3. To determine the algorithm for organizing the dialogue of adults and children in the developmental environment of early age groups.

4. Materials and methods

The following research methods were used to achieve the goal and carry out the tasks:

- analysis of scientific sources to understand the essence of the studied phenomenon;
- analysis, synthesis, systematization and generalization of the concepts "dialogue", "interaction", "dialogic interaction";
- theoretical modeling – to substantiate the models of dialogic interaction of adults and children in the developmental environment of early age groups.

5. Research results

The results of the theoretical analysis of the study of the phenomenon of dialogic interaction of adults and young children show that in most scientific sources dialogue is considered as a form, method and means of social contacts, which is realized by the individual in subject-subject interaction. Development and implementation of the model of organization of dialogic interaction involves the search and finding the pedagogical meaning of what is happening, its educational interpretation based on the personal meanings of young children.

Based on this understanding of the essence of this process, in the psychological and pedagogical literature, the types and forms of interaction between child and adult are considered on various grounds:

- by the style of pedagogical interaction: authoritarian, democratic and liberal [7];
- by the nature of the attitude to interaction: compromise, adaptation, ignoring (neglect), rivalry, competition, cooperation [8];
- by the nature of pedagogical influences: authoritarian ("do as I do"); cooperation ("let's do it together");
- partnerships ("let's think about how to do it") [9];
- by the degree of subjectivity: educational-disciplinary, personality-oriented [9].

Educational influences, focused on dialogic interaction able to stimulate speech and interpersonal interaction between children, are just beginning to be developed and do not have wide practical application. Thus, studying the problem of the effectiveness of dialogue, A. Harash, identifies such types of personal inclusion of the communicator in the "sphere of life" of the individual as authoritarian and dialogical. Authoritarian inclusion involves the antagonistic opposition of "one's own" to "another's" and oneself to others. Dialogic inclusion is based on respect for the sovereignty of another's life and another's consciousness.

E. Levinas [10] identified three types of dialogue:

- 1) integration, or positive, i.e. one that involves the satisfaction of the point of view of only one of the participants in the dialogue; the point of view of the other participant in the dialogue is completely excluded;
- 2) identification or negative – when the interlocutors with equal success deny each other's point of view;
- 3) synthetic or symbolic – a dialogue of reconciliation, when the search for truth with equal interest of both parties.

The classification of styles of pedagogical communication, proposed by V. Kan-Kalik, is interesting within the limits of our research. The styles, singled out by him, are named as: communication on the basis of enthusiasm for joint creative activity; communication on the basis of friendly relations; communication-distance; communication-intimidation; communication-flirting.

Based on the following ideas about dialogue, the development of dialogue interaction of adults and young children in the educational space of PEI, it is necessary to focus on solving the following tasks:

- establishing emotional contact between participants in educational interaction;

- mastering verbal and nonverbal means of communication;
- ability to perform actions together with other participants in the educational process.

In accordance with these tasks, we distinguish the following types of models of dialogue interaction of adults with young children in the developmental environment of PEI early age groups:

- interaction that encourages the child to active cognition;
 - reorientation of the child's behavior in interaction with an adult;
 - supportive interaction.
- Consider more detailed models.

Interaction that encourages the child to active cognition. The basis of worldview and cognitive development of young children is the material world. The material world exists for the child in the context of his/her subjectivity, the significance of this world for him/her personally in the artistic, figurative, holistic understanding of him/herself and the world. Therefore, cognitive development occurs during interaction with objects, mastering texts, actions in a specially created space. The core of such a system is the active action of the child. Only due to the active activity of the child is the knowledge of the world around (Fig. 1).

Fig. 1. Scheme of the model of interaction that encourages the child to active cognition

Organization of work with objects. At the initial stage, the adult names the chosen object, encourages the child to examine it, helps to repeat certain qualities (color, shape, size) and properties (rolling, jumping, folding, etc.), determines how to act with the object. Later, the adult expands the child's understanding of what other objects the selected object has similar qualities and properties (the ball is shaped like a balloon, snowball, apple; color – such as a handkerchief, airplane, cucumber, etc.; in size – a ball like a bear, like a box). The child must realize not only the common but also the differences between objects.

Organization of work with texts. Involve children in actively listening to texts, told by the adult. It is better to tell short texts twice in a row, ensuring children's activity during listening by performing imitation movements, using visual aids, combining a story with a display of table theater figures, staging with a flannelgraph, playing field or didactic frame. During the second story,

it is worth remembering the content of the fairy tale, performing tasks that allow you to perform motor exercises (jump like a frog, show how to find a glove, etc.). Continue to work with the text by independent play of the children with figures of table theater, viewing of illustrations.

Organization of work on mastering actions. First, the teacher, attracting the child's attention, shows him/her the action with the object, which is characterized by this action: pour water, pour cereal, roll the machine. He/she further draws attention to the fact that this action can be performed with other objects: you can roll not only cars but also balls, even balloons, emphasizing that different versions of the same action depending on the object have their own specifics.

The next step is to master this action in a new space: roll a ball or a car on a flat track directly into the goal – the gate, ride on the maze or on a sloping board (in this case, we can roll down or vice versa). The educator can then ask the children to perform the action not with their hands, but with the help of special devices or tools: to roll a balloon around the maze with a gymnastic stick, a soft stick or a fan.

Organization of work in a specially *created* space. In addition to mastering the material world and mastering actions, educational interaction can be directed to the child's mastery of **space**. By space we mean a certain cell in a group room: it can be tabletops, set next to each other, the floor, which is taped as a maze, frame, or wall, which is fixed to the water supply, and so on. Expanding the space for learning new actions with iconic objects trains the child in orienteering, enriches the cognitive and life experience of the child, promotes the development of his/her independence.

It is necessary to begin work on mastering space with acquaintance with its properties and actions, which we can do in it: the adult helps the children to find out what certain marks mean (stickers on a tabletop/locker/chair/bed, etc. of various figures or icons, arrows). They illustrate the rules that must be followed (option – movement in the maze in only one direction).

The next step should be to enrich the child's experience with different options for actions, movements in this space (you can not only put your hands on the proposed stickers, but also combine it with rhythmic movements, accompanied by music). Next, the adult can ask the children to try the action in a specially created location for action with other objects: roll a ring of pyramids at a gate of a certain color, ride a jumper through a maze on a sloping board, and then a soft fluffy ball and compare how they rolled. You can complicate the action by using tools and special devices. In the water basin to fill the tank, give the children two tools - a strainer and a spoon. The child has to choose, which tool can be used to collect water in the tank, and which will help him/her to catch objects from the water [11].

Reorientation of the child's behavior in interaction with the adult. The child at an early age begins to feel in a sense a person independent of the adult, which leads to controversy: on the one hand – the child still depends on adult help and support, on the other – defends his/her own independent attempts.

Reorientation is an approach to the child's behavior that involves natural and logical changes in unwanted behavior of the child, which strengthens the child's sense of self-worth and shapes his/her character, because the child learns how to act with objects, ways to communicate with others, masters the rules of interaction with others.

Models of reorientation dialogue interaction with young children:

– Sandwich (praise-scold-support: how fast you run – remember, you have to run on the track – try it, you will succeed!);

– Steps (we already know how to show a new action, we ask you to act independently: Mariyka, roll the balls into a box, look, you can still roll the ball with a stick. Now try it yourself!);

– Triplets (action-feeling-perspective: Oh, how Mikita jumps like a bunny! I like it so much! You will learn and will jump even higher than a bunny!);

– Sample (standard-observation-result: – Sashko, when you address someone you have to speak loudly! See how I call Svitlana loudly! You will address loudly – you will be heard – you will be heard!).

Supportive interaction. One of the main tasks of adults who are close to the child is to help him/her form a positive image of him/herself, to realize their value and uniqueness. Supportive interaction is a process of joint determination with the child of his/her own interests, goals, opportunities and ways to overcome obstacles (problems), which provides an opportunity to independently achieve the desired results in learning, self-education, communication.

Implementation of pedagogical support involves respect for the child, which is manifested in the educator's knowledge of individual characteristics of the child, in showing confidence in him/her, kindness, sensitivity, compassion, benevolence, heartfelt care, empathy for the individual, which involves the desire and ability to feel another as yourself, to take his/her position, to understand the inner world of the child. Among speech practices, we prefer those that are aimed at positive support of the partner, while own interests are pushed to the background [12, 13].

Allocation of pedagogical support in a special direction in professional pedagogical activity entails a change in the position of the teacher in the "fight against ..." to the position – "I will help you".

The ultimate goal of pedagogical support is the child's personality, his/her ability to solve problems and cope with life's difficulties. To achieve this goal, the teacher does not have a direct impact on the child's personality, but assists him/her in solving pressing problems. Personality becomes an internal resource that helps children to solve their own difficulties [14].

When providing psychological support, you should avoid the mistakes that adults usually make in this way. First of all, it is the creation of dependence of the child on the adult, extremely high requirements to him/her, etc. Therefore, the real support of a child by an

adult should be based on respect for his/her "Me", opportunities, all the positive things he/she has.

Support interaction models:

– emotional support (stabilization of the emotional state of the child, activation of the development of the emotional sphere of children and assistance in mastering the skills of emotional regulation);

– resource support (creation of favorable external conditions (environment) for the mental and biological existence and development of the child);

– co-existence support (situational) (organization of a humane environment (humanistic relations, communication, creative activity, psychological climate, etc.) as a product of activity of children and adults).

An algorithm for organizing dialogue interaction

1. I watch what the child is doing now.

2. I feel and analyze what he/she needs now, what he/she expects from me.

3. I give him/her what he/she needs.

The unwillingness of the majority of educators to use speech formulas and reactions in interaction with young children for each type of dialogue interaction made it difficult to achieve the desired results and showed the need to enrich the content of professional training and retraining of teachers in this aspect.

6. Conclusions

1. Reflection on the basis of studying the theoretical foundations of the stated problem made it possible to clarify the essence of the concepts of "dialogue", "interaction", "dialogue interaction". Dialogue interaction in the research is considered as a linguistic and cultural phenomenon, because it is dialogue that connects a person with the outside world, creates a basis for mutual understanding between young children and adults. Dialogue interaction is aimed at solving the following tasks: establishing emotional contact between participants in educational interaction; mastering verbal and nonverbal means of communication; ability to perform actions together with other participants in the educational process.

2. As a result of the conducted research the following models of dialogical interaction between young children and adults in the developmental environment of the early age group are characterized: interaction that encourages the child to active cognition; reorientation of the child's behavior in interaction with an adult; supportive interaction.

3. The algorithm of the organization of such interaction is defined: I observe actions of the kid at present; I feel and analyze what he/she needs now, what he/she expects from me; with the help of appropriate speech formulas and actions I help him/her to realize his/her needs.

Conflict of interests

The authors declare that they have no conflicts of interest.

References

1. Ozadovska, L. (2007). Paradyhma dialohichnosti v suchasnomu myslenni. Kyiv: Parapan, 166.
2. Artur, S. J. (1997). The german and russian ideology on M. Bakhtin. London: Routledge, 213.
3. Abulkhanova, K. A. (1999). Psikhologija i soznanie lichnosti. Moscow: Moskovskii psikhologo-sotcialnyi institut; Voronezh: Izdatelstvo NPO «MODEK», 224.
4. Volkova, E. N. (1998). Subektnost pedagoga: teoriia i praktika. Moscow, 50.
5. Diakonov, G. V. (2009). Osnovy dialogicheskogo podkhoda v psikhologicheskoi nauke i praktike. Kyiv, 573.
6. Bekh, I. D. (2003). Vikhovannia osobistosti. Kyiv: Libid, 344.
7. Turek, I. (2010). Didaktika. Bratislava: Iura Edition, 598.
8. Nikolaienko, S. O. (2013). Sutnisni kharakterystyky pedahohichnogo spilkuvannia. Pedahohika i psykhologhiia. Kharkiv: Skhidnoukrainska orhanizatsiia «Tsentri pedahohichnykh doslidzhen», 96–100.
9. Petrovskii, A. V. (1996). Lichnost. deiatelnost. kollektiv. Moscow: Politizdat, 255.
10. Levinas, E. (2006). Put k drugomu. Saint Petersburg: Izd-vo S.-Peterburgskogo universiteta, 239.
11. Gavrish, N. V., Bezsonova, O. K. (2021). Tekhnologiiia stimuliuвання prirodnoho rozvitku ditei rannogo viku. World science: problems, prospects and innovations. Toronto Perfect Publishing, 253.
12. Floyd, K. (1997). Communicating affection in dyadic relationships: An assessment of behavior and expectancies. *Communication Quarterly*, 45 (1), 68–80. doi: <http://doi.org/10.1080/01463379709370045>
13. Weigel, D. J., Ballard-Reisch, D. S. (1999). The influence of marital duration on the use of relationship maintenance behaviors. *Communication Reports*, 12 (2), 59–70. doi: <http://doi.org/10.1080/08934219909367711>
14. Kobilchenko, V. V. (2017). Teoretichni osnovi psikhologo-pedagogichnogo suprovodu molodshikh shkolariv z porushenniami zoru. Poltava: TOV «Firma «Tekhservis», 367.

Received date 20.04.2022

Accepted date 23.05.2022

Published date 31.05.2022

Natalia Gavrish*, Doctor of Pedagogical Sciences, Professor, Boyarka, Kyiv region, Ukraine

Olga Bezsonova, PhD, Director, Municipal Preschool Educational Institution No. 67 "Sunny" of the General Type of Kramatorsk City Council, M. Priymachenko str., 23, Kramatorsk, Ukraine, 84331

**Corresponding author: Natalia Gavrish, e-mail: n.rodinaga@ukr.net*